

HOMEROOM GUIDANCE PROGRAM: INSTITUTIONALIZING AN ESSENTIAL NON-ACADEMIC SCHEDULE IN THE CITY SCHOOLS DIVISION OF TANAUAN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11425676>

ABSTRACT

DepEd Order No. 31, s. 2012 sets aside a time for the Homeroom period. This underlines the importance of homeroom in the school schedule. Students can easily be influenced by the environment and the media, which do not always have wholesome ideas to share. Learners need the proper guidance they can get and Homeroom periods can be one of those opportunities where they can be guided. This research is initiated to pay more attention to how Homeroom classes are conducted. The researchers will try to revisit the conduct of the homeroom periods in Tanauan City Division. If the data gathered shows inadequacy, then, modifying structure, themes, and perspective might help educators and learners get the most out of this period. Correspondingly, developing a module for homeroom classes can help deliver it according to what the Department of Education intends it to be.

Keywords: *Homeroom, Guidance, Program, Schedule, Theme*

INTRODUCTION

DepEd Order No. 31, s. 2012 provides a time for the Homeroom period. This underlines the importance of homeroom in the school schedule. Learners need the proper guidance they can get and Homeroom periods can be one of those opportunities where they can be guided. Teenage learners can be heavily influenced by the media and the environment. But the contents of the media may not always portray wholesome features

and the environment where some learners live may not be conducive to their moral and personal growth. Because of these matters, the school remains to be a relevant avenue where they can holistically grow and develop virtues that will make them worthwhile citizens when they grow older (Sutton, 2020).

To form and develop worthwhile citizens have never been so important in these times when values can easily be corrupted by irresponsible use of technology. Accordingly, there is a consensus among the older generation that young people today do not have the same values practiced before. Values formation seems to have been disregarded. In school, the homeroom period is one schedule when students can get guidance to put their lives in proper perspective. But this period of the class schedule can be spent aimlessly without any program prepared by the persons concerned.

This research was initiated to pay more attention to how Homeroom classes are conducted. There are a number of literature related to this topic, but, there is more to be explored. The researchers looked into the conduct of the homeroom period in the City Schools Division of Tanauan. The data gathered showed inadequacy, therefore modifying structure, themes and perspective might help educators and learners get the most out of this period. Correspondingly, developing a program and accompanying module for homeroom classes can be helpful in delivering it according to what the Department of Education intends it to be.

Research Questions

In educational settings, the provision of comprehensive guidance and support services plays a pivotal role in fostering students' academic achievement, socio-emotional well-being, and overall personal development. Homeroom guidance programs serve as fundamental platforms for delivering such support within schools, aiming to address students' diverse needs and equip them with essential life skills.

This study seeks to address the following key questions:

1. How is homeroom class being taught in terms of:
 - 1.1 Preparation
 - 1.2 Introduction
 - 1.3 Activity
 - 1.4 Summary?
2. What possible themes or lessons can be taught in the homeroom period?
3. What program should be created to truly harness the potential of the homeroom period?

METHODOLOGY

The target population of this study is Tanauan City Division secondary school heads, guidance counselors and teachers. Teachers who are current or previous class advisers are the respondents of the questionnaires because usually, they are the ones who conduct homeroom classes. Likewise, guidance counselors were involved in this study because they should be the ones who provide topics for Homeroom discussion. School heads involvement in this study was crucial because of their role as leaders of the schools. They should be knowledgeable about the results and implications of this division-wide research.

The study utilized researcher-made questionnaire, interviews and focus group discussions. The researchers asked the permission of the Schools Division Superintendent and concerned Supervisor for the conduct of the research. The questionnaire was given to secondary school teachers based on the sample size determination made (Kibuacha, 2021). Likewise, the school heads and guidance counselors were interviewed regarding the conduct of the homeroom classes in their respective schools. Focus group discussion was conducted with school heads, guidance counselors, and teachers for some possible modifications in Homeroom classes and creation of a Homeroom Class module that will be used in the Division.

The data collected was collated and tabulated to facilitate analysis. It was organized and categorized using the research questions to be able to identify the themes and patterns to be presented (Caulfield, 2023). To answer the particular questions raised in this study, data were treated carefully, classified and methodically organized according to the certain point established in this study.

RESULTS

1. How is homeroom class being taught?

Homeroom Structure		
1. Preparation	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1.1 asks assistance from Homeroom Guidance Committee (or equivalent) for theme or topic for discussion	2.93	Oftentimes
1.2 reflects on the learners' needs	3.58	Always
1.3 sets aim/s or objective/s	3.55	Always
2. Introduction	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
2.1 gives the learners information about the topic	3.57	Always
2.2 tells learners what are expected from them	3.55	Always

2.3 creates a climate of oneness and acceptance among the members of the group to avoid uncomfortable moments during the activity	3.55	Always
3. Activity	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
3.1 considers activities which are relevant to learners' personal experiences	3.44	Oftentimes
3.2 provides materials or asks learners' to bring necessary materials	3.34	Oftentimes
3.3 processes activity to truly harness its effect	3.39	Oftentimes
4. Summary	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
4.1 gives reflection questions or prompts to diagnose learners' understanding	3.44	Oftentimes
4.2 asks learners for feedback or questions	3.47	Oftentimes
4.3 relates previous and future themes to the current topic whenever merited	3.43	Oftentimes

4.00 – 3.50 - Always (A)

3.49 – 2.50 - Oftentimes (O)

2.49 – 1.50 - Seldom (S)

1.49 and below - Never (N)

2. What possible themes or lessons can be taught in the homeroom period?

Grade 7		
Rank	Topic	Frequency
1	Student Profile	31
2	School Discipline	30
3	Cleanliness in the Classroom	29
4	Bullying	27
5	Report Card	23
6	Character Formation	21
8	Parent-Teacher Association	19
8	Family Relationship	19
8	Absenteeism	19
10	Love and Responsibility	17

For grade 7, the topic of Student Profile had the most frequency. As new students, the advisers should get pertinent information about them. The information gathered from the students will be helpful to know their background and better help them in cases when they fail the different standards of the school.

Grade 8		
Rank	Topic	Frequency
2	Class Officers	15
2	Report Card	15
2	Emotional Intelligence	15
4	Managing Conflicts	14
5.5	Personal Goal Setting	12
5.5	Absenteeism	12
7	Home Visitation	10
8	Leadership	8
9.5	Budgeting of Resources	6
9.5	Media Savvy (Effects of Media)	6

The topic of Class Officers had the most frequency among grade 8 advisers. The grade 8 advisers did not ignore their importance for a functional classroom, and they are worth discussing in homeroom periods. Class officers are the representatives of the teachers when they are not around.

Grade 9		
Rank	Topic	Frequency
1	Character Formation	29
2	School Discipline	27
3	Love and Responsibility	24
4.5	Student Profile	23
4.5	Cleanliness in the Classroom	23
6	Family Relationship	20
7.5	Personal Goal Setting	18
7.5	Building Self-esteem	18
9	Absenteeism	17
10	Managing Conflicts	16

Character Formation is the topic with the highest frequency among grade 9 advisers. Grade 9 level students might be at the peak of their curiosity to explore matters beyond what is acceptable to school norms which is why they face some issues with school authorities. The key remains proper guidance to avoid untoward incidents. Homeroom can be the most appropriate time to do this and character formation is highly appropriate for their level.

Grade 10		
Rank	Topic	Frequency
1	Student Profile	24
2	Character Formation	23
3.5	Family Relationships	18

3.5	Cleanliness in the Classroom	18
5	School Discipline	17
6.5	Love and Responsibility	16
6.5	Building Self-esteem	16
9	Parent-Teacher Association	15
9	Health and Grooming	15
9	Absenteeism	15

The grade 10 advisers highly ranked topics on Student Profile, Character Formation, and Family Relationships. Worth emphasizing is the choice of character formation and family relationships among them (Kapunan, 2004). Considering the needs of their students, the grade 10 advisers made appropriate choices. Providing topics regarding character and relationship to students can guide them to make correct responses in the situations they encounter.

Grade 11		
Rank	Topic	Frequency
1	School Discipline	7
3.5	Student Profile	5
3.5	Love and Responsibility	5
3.5	Building Self-esteem	5
3.5	Cleanliness in the Classroom	5
7	Character Formation	4
7	Parent-Teacher Association	4
7	Student Evaluation	4
9.5	Values, Vision and Mission	3
9.5	Class Officers	3

School Discipline had the most frequency among grade 11 advisers. Reaching senior high school does not guarantee that students are already disciplined. Underlining discipline even at this stage will be helpful to students to control themselves as they enter their adulthood.

Grade 12		
Rank	Topic	Frequency
1	School Discipline	6
2	Family Relationship	5
5	Vision for Homeroom	4
5	Personal Goal Setting	4
5	Study and Reading Strategies	4
5	Managing Conflicts	4
5	Building Self-esteem	4
9	Values, Vision and Mission	3

9	Character Formation	3
9	Leadership	3

Like the grade 11, the grade 12 advisers chose school discipline as their primary topic. Discipline is truly a factor in being able to contribute to the community. The graduating students cannot be fully contributing and functioning individuals to society unless they are taught the non-negotiable importance of discipline, especially at the last year of their high school life.

DISCUSSION

Though not primarily a content subject, homeroom can be given preparation and attention like the usual content subjects (Kelly et al., 2005). The result of the study regarding its delivery is indicated in the table. The research divided the structure of homeroom into four parts namely, preparation, introduction, activity and summary. For the first part, introduction, the indicator, asks for assistance from Homeroom Guidance Committee (or equivalent) for theme or topic for discussion, had the lowest weighted mean of 2.93. This indicates that the conduct of homeroom is not centralized. Advisers do homeroom classes from their initiative. If the Homeroom Guidance Committee is established and had a ready program, the weighted mean could have not been this low.

The second part, introduction, also had three items. The highest weighted mean among them is gives the learners information about the topic. The other two had the same weighted mean. The low weighted mean of creates a climate of oneness and acceptance among the members of the group to avoid uncomfortable moments during the activity can be connected to the lack of briefing or preparation on the part of the advisers coming from authorities concerned in delivering homeroom classes.

The third part, activity, had the item considers activities which are relevant to learners' personal experiences with the highest weighted mean. This shows the sensitivity of the advisers to diagnose the needs of the learners (Ridnouer,2006).

As for the fourth part, summary, asks learners for feedback or questions had the highest weighted mean. While the lowest was relates previous and future themes to the current topic whenever merited. This indicates lack of continuity and coherence of topics or matters discussed and can be associated again to the deficiency of a program for homeroom classes. Accordingly, Mendoza (2005) articulated the importance of homeroom as it provides right conduct and good manners. These two are crucial for developing adolescents to be good citizens as they mature. Hence, preparation for homeroom classes should not be overlooked.

Conclusions

1. It can be seen from the result that the conduct of the homeroom classes can still be improved. It is not centralized, that is, there is no one authority who tells the appropriate

class structure nor topics to be discussed. Likewise, it can be deduced that the conduct of homeroom class depended on the adviser's initiative.

2. From the result of the questionnaire, some of the topics which emerged were: School Discipline, Love and Responsibility, Character Formation, Student Profiling and Cleanliness in the Classroom among others. These topics are highly relevant and based on the needs observed by the advisers. Topics such as these can affect the class dynamics for the entire duration of the school year.

3. Based on the result of the study, a homeroom program can be created to facilitate its delivery. There should be a governing body or committee which will structure the class program for unified administration. Making an institutionalized homeroom program will benefit all advisers during their homeroom time and not only those who have initiative in conducting it.

Recommendations

Homeroom class has its own merits. Learning is not only confined to the content subjects. Some students are very much in need of personal human learning to make sense of their personal lives. Properly conducting homeroom classes and discussing topics relevant to students' lives can answer some of their personal and relational needs. It is therefore recommended that a program be developed regarding class structure and topics to be discussed.

Topics picked by the advisers should be highly considered by the committee. These topics should be appropriately researched and a module should be made out from them. Advisers should be well informed as to how to deliver the topics in the module.

Homeroom class should be given attention (Breux, 2005). The content subjects do not cover all the needs of growing young learners. There are matters beyond content subjects which deals with the emotional and relational dimensions of learners. Homeroom can be one of the class schedules which can address these dimensions.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Permission was asked from authorities to conduct this research. Before making the respondents answer the questionnaire, they were given an informed consent form so that there would be no coercion involved in conducting the study. Those who were involved were informed of the purposes of the data that were asked of them.

Sensitive issues were carefully handled with respect to the differences of views (Resnik, 2020). Anonymity of respondents was strictly observed unless the study necessitates

otherwise, but if such happens, authorization from those concerned will be graciously asked by the researchers.

Acknowledgments

This study could not have been possible without the generous help of several people who motivated, inspired, assisted, and supported our entire endeavor. Their names are not just written in this manuscript but engrained in every fiber and vein of the researchers' hearts. Their names are gratefully acknowledged, and their inspiration will always be treasured.

To the Republic of the Philippines, Department of Education, Region IV-A CALABARZON (4th Cycle Basic Education Research Fund (BERF)) for the fund given to accomplish this research.

To Ms. Teresita C. Casquejo and Ms. Florinda Casquejo-Gagasa, Education Program Supervisor at the City Schools Division of Tanauan for their inspiration and unwavering support;

To Ms. Maria Liza M. Faustino, Senior Education Program Specialist, Planning & Research at the City Schools Division of Tanauan for her encouragement;

To the respondents of this study;

And above all, to Our Lord Jesus Christ through the intercession of His Mother Mary for the grace and gift of life and talent.

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